

Structural Analysis of Voice of Nigeria (VON) in the Digital Age

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Abstract

This study investigated the operational and managerial structures of VON, the extent of its digital technology integration, the challenges of restructuring for the digital age and strategies adopted for global competitiveness. Guided by media ecology and media convergence theories, the study employed a qualitative design. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with 20 purposively selected management staff of VON and analysed thematically. Findings showed that VON operates a state-supervised, hierarchical structure, with its headquarters in Abuja, Nigeria's capital and zonal offices across the country's six geopolitical zones. To support digital transformation, VON established Digital media and IT departments and expanded its online platforms, live streaming, mobile applications and social media engagement, which facilitates substantial integration of digital technologies into its organisational processes. Nevertheless, the international radio station faced persistent challenges, which include funding deficits, outdated infrastructure, limited staff training, bureaucratic bottlenecks, legal restrictions on commercial activities, low staff salaries and non-payment of staff allowances for official assignments. To remain globally relevant and competitive, VON adopted multiplatform content distribution, reactivated DRM (Digital Radio Mondiale), and implemented audience engagement programmes. The study concluded that although VON has progressed in structural adaptation and digital integration, addressing resource, infrastructural and capacity gaps is crucial to consolidating its role as Nigeria's authoritative voice in international broadcasting. The study recommended increased federal funding and appointment of an individual with proven broadcast experience and strong commitment to staff welfare and organisational development as Director-General of VON. This would enhance leadership effectiveness.

Keywords: Voice of Nigeria, Traditional Media Structure, Broadcast Station Management

Introduction

Traditional media refers to established forms of mass communication that existed before the emergence of the Internet (Anyanwu, Imiti & Anyanwu, 2024). Print (newspapers and magazines), audiovisual media like terrestrial radio and television constitute these media forms through which information is disseminated to broad and heterogeneous audiences without direct feedback and interaction (Albadri, 2023). Like other corporate bodies, the operational and managerial structures of traditional media houses are

characterised by a hierarchical and centralised system of communication (Porcu, Hermans & Broersma, 2024). This top-down system often resembles a pyramid whereby corporate decisions are made by a small group of individuals at the top (Anter, 2023).

The operational and managerial structures of media organisations continue to witness notable challenges and changes before and after the digital age in developing countries. Voice of Nigeria (VON) is a strong case for studying this shift. VON was established in 1990 by the administration of the former Nigerian military president, General Ibrahim Babangida. VON's initial launch as an autonomous station was surrounded by financial constraints. At establishment, there was no budgetary provision for it (Akinreti, 2024). That consequently delayed its operational take off till 1992 (Egbuna & Iyamu, 2020).

VON competes for audiences alongside other international news organisations like BBC, VOA and RFI. These stations have sustained transnational reach in the digital era (Elewodal, 2017). VON has also been adapting modern technologies in its content production and distribution. Despite these adaptations, structural challenges continue to hinder traditional broadcast stations such as VON (Akinreti, 2024). This article examines how VON has redesigned its structures, to what extent it has integrated digital technologies, what challenges it faces and what strategies sustain its global relevance and competitiveness.

Statement of the Problem

Platformisation compels broadcast stations to align structures and workflows with digital standards (Flew, 2024). For public broadcasters, redesign must protect autonomy and public value, while maintaining universality of service (Moe, 2024). Yet peer-reviewed work on VON's structural analysis is scarce. Most studies emphasise audience or policy dynamics rather than managerial and operational reconfiguration. This study, therefore, addresses the limited availability of scholarly research in the public domain on VON's operational and managerial structures.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the current operational and managerial structures of VON and do they support digital broadcasting?
2. To what extent has VON integrated digital technologies into its content production and distribution processes?
3. What challenges does VON encounter in restructuring its operations for the digital age?
4. What strategies has VON adopted to remain relevant and competitive globally?

Analogue Era versus Digital Age

The evolution of broadcasting from the analogue era to the digital age is regarded by scholars as the most significant shift in the history of this sector of audiovisual information dissemination. In the analogue era, for example, the production and transmission of media content were one-way. This production and transmission process relied heavily on hardware (Albadri, 2023). Media content used to be produced for some

platforms, like radio and television. Again, the transmission of this content was on established broadcast bands, AM/FM for radio and VHF/UHF for over-the-air television (Nielsen & Fletcher, 2023).

Audience access was restricted by geographical location in addition to the quality of the signal. There were reception probabilities sensitive to transmission and interference conditions in the bands. Interaction was minimal; as it was typically limited to audience letters to stations and live phone-in programmes rather than continuous, platform-mediated feedback. Such structure specified the restrictions and inflexibility of analogue broadcasting. On the contrast, the digital media age represents the opposite of the aforementioned (Dragomir & Túnéz López, 2024).

VON Frequencies

VON broadcasts its news and programmes in eight languages namely, Arabic, English, French, Fulfulde, Igbo, Kiswahili and Yoruba. Similarly, the international station also has eight frequencies. Each of these frequencies is for a particular region among the regions of the world. This positions VON as an international radio station of global reach (Bin Hyacinth, 2018). In the analogue era, VON transmitted its programmes to its heterogenous audiences across the world through its frequencies. Egbuna & Iyamu, (2020) list these frequencies as follows:

Region	Broadcast Frequencies (kHz)
North Africa and Europe	11770, 15120, 17800, 21450
Middle East (including Turkey, France, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Egypt)	11770, 15120, 17800
North Africa (including Morocco, Libya, Tunisia, Egypt, Sudan)	9690, 11770
India (including Pakistan, Iran, Singapore, Philippines)	11770, 15120, 17800, 21450
West Africa (including Senegal, Burkina Faso, Liberia, Ghana)	7255, 9690
Caribbean (including Brazil, Venezuela, Cuba, Mexico, Colombia, Guatemala, Texas)	11770, 15120, 17800, 21450
North America (including USA, Canada)	15120, 17800, 21450, 2650
East Africa (including Kenya, Uganda, Ethiopia, Tanzania, Sudan, DRC)	11770, 15120, 7255, 9690
Australia (including New Zealand, Indonesia, Sumatra, Borneo)	15120, 17800, 22750, 26250
Central Africa (including Cameroon, Central African Republic, Gabon, DRC)	7255, 9690
Southern Africa (including Zambia, Burundi, Rwanda, Namibia, South Africa, Mozambique, Zimbabwe)	7255, 9690, 11770, 15120

The Ecosystem of a Broadcast Media Station

Broadcast operations rely on interdependent roles across editorial, engineering, IT, production, languages, and support services (Momoh, 2021). Over-rigid hierarchies can inhibit innovation and responsiveness during digital transformation (Besio, Dobusch, & Schoeneborn, 2024). Effective structures balance clarity of authority with cross-functional collaboration (Porcu et al., 2024).

Structural Expansion in VON

From 1962–1990, external service functions were under Radio Nigeria. With autonomy in 1990, VON was structured on three departments, namely: News and Programmes, Engineering and Administration/Finance (Egbuna & Iyamu, 2020). Subsequent reforms included:

- 2007: IT carved out of Engineering.
- 2012: Strategic Planning & Corporate Development (SPCD) established.
- 2019: Digital Media created from News; Programmes split into Languages and Operations; Administration split into HR and General Services; Finance split into Finance, Audit, Procurement (Akinreti, 2024).

Although, these operational changes institutionalise the digital turn in VON, they however may result in creating unnecessary duplications or inter-departmental rivalry if not properly coordinated.

Leadership and Performance

VON’s analogue-era prominence witnessed live coverage of major regional and global events, coincided with broadcast-experienced leadership (Akinreti, 2024). Subsequent decline in VON’s glory was attributed to appointment of CEOs who were misaligned with broadcast requirements and to chronic underfunding, both of which eroded training, on-ground newsgathering, and production capacity (Egbuna & Iyamu, 2020).

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on media ecology and media convergence theories. Media ecology theory asserts that media houses are environments that shape institutions,

operations, and audience relations. In platform-dominated contexts, shifts from analogue to multi-platform systems necessitate structural and managerial redesign. Thus, in line with Madouh & Kwon's (2023) study, this explains why VON's structure must change to help project ecosystem-level pressures that hinder reforms. Again, it also directly supports assessing VON's structures, as contained in Research Question (RQ) 1 of this study, and the constraints, as stated in RQ 3.

On the other hand, media convergence theory explains the way change is operationalised (Hase, Boczek & Scharrow, 2023; Nielsen & Fletcher, 2023). It focuses on integrating channels and revolutionising content production for compatible dissemination. For audience interaction opportunities, newsrooms modify operations and redesign their contents on social media like Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, X and. Such operational redesign, therefore, explains the processes of content production and distribution of VON, which is in line with RQ 2 of this paper. This equally analyses VON's strategies to remain relevant and competitive globally, as mentioned in RQ 4.

Empirical Review

Currently, there exists an empirical literature vacuum on VON's operational and managerial structures in the analogue era and the digital age. To fill this gap, empirical studies on regional and international radio and television stations of similar status to VON were used as the basis for this review. Worldwide, studies have highlighted how restructuring workflows is necessary for stations to remain relevant. For example, Rostamian & Moradi Kamreh, (2024), examined the opportunities and challenges of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into broadcast operations and management. Through a qualitative design and semi-structured interviews with 15 purposively selected industry professionals, they found that aligning the structures of organisations with digital technologies improves production of programmes, interactions with audiences, and efficiency of their operations. The relationship of the above with VON, as the entity being studied here is that, VON's creation of an online section in year 2000, and the subsequent elevation of the section to a full Digital Media Department in 2019 reflect similar organisational adjustments aimed at integrating new technologies into VON's broadcasting processes.

It is pertinent to state that restructuring of broadcast stations has also been driven by the way audiences receive broadcast messages. That was why Harliantara, Widiarto, Prasetyo, Wahyunto & Sjachro (2025) investigated how radio stations are redefining their roles in response to and satisfaction of their audiences. Through observation and document analysis, their study revealed that stations continuously establish their online presence and diversify the way they deliver their broadcast content in order to remain relevant and competitive. This structural redefinition is closely in line with VON's operational expansion from purely terrestrial broadcasting to a hybrid model that combines digital streaming and traditional shortwave transmission.

Furthermore, the extent of digital integration in producing and distributing broadcast content is also an indication of how traditional media adapts digital technologies. Zondi (2024) investigated how digital media technologies redesigned the operations of radio in simplifying audience interactions through a qualitative case study of South African stations. He also found that integrating digital technologies into

operations of a station extends their reach beyond boundaries. Zondi's (2024) findings resonate with VON's adoption of livestreaming, mobile apps, and multiple online platforms to expand its access to its listeners and engage with them.

Some scholars have assessed the specific case of VON's digital footprint. Egbuna & Iyamu (2020) through observation and document analysis, found that the international station's digital presence includes real-time email correspondence with audiences, mobile app access and availability on platforms such as Simple Radio, Radio Garden, TuneIn, YouTube, Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), and TikTok. Alongside these digital innovations, VON continues to operate eight shortwave frequencies in multiple languages to ensure that it serves both its global online audiences and traditional listeners.

Despite the presence of these advancements in VON and other Nigerian broadcast stations, major challenges remain in aligning the structures of these stations with digital standards. To assess the effects digitalisation on Nigeria broadcast industry, Sanusi, Oyegoke & Ojewumi (2025) surveyed 321 broadcast stakeholders and audience members to evaluate the effects of digitalisation on Nigeria's broadcast industry. They found that although there had been some improvement in broadcast content quality and accessibility of stations to audiences, however, high costs of operations, deficits in infrastructure, low digital literacy, and regulatory barriers remain the major challenges. As a Nigerian radio station, VON equally faces the same challenges.

From a global perspective, Dragomir & Túnnez López (2024) examined how public service media (PSM) in developed countries adapt to platformisation. Drawing on interviews, policy reviews and institutional analysis, the authors found that even well-funded PSMs face challenges in striking a balance between technological innovation and the mandates of public service. For VON, such challenges are exacerbated by inadequate funding, periodic off-air episodes due to diesel shortages and legal prohibitions against commercial advertising under Section 11(1) of the *VON Decree 15 of 1991* (Egbuna & Iyamu, 2020).

Audience engagement remains another critical dimension. Hassan & Sam (2024) assessed the incorporation of social media into conventional broadcasting in Nigeria. Through questionnaires and interviews with staff members of NTA, Radio Nigeria, Arise TV and RayPower FM, the study revealed that integration of social media into traditional media enhances audience participation. However, they also found that such enhancement is hampered by network instability, funding shortfalls, and unreliable electricity. For VON, embedding interactive audience strategies into its daily operations has been essential in maximising the benefits of its digital technologies.

The question of relevance in the digital age is addressed by Deacon, Smith, & Wring (2024), who combined audience metrics with industry data to assess the operations of traditional media. They identified four challenges: reach, resources, reputation, and relevance. Despite these challenges, they concluded that traditional media remain crucial for agenda-setting and content verification, with online platforms often depending on the reporting of traditional media. This study suggests that VON retains value as an authoritative source for local and international audiences seeking verified information about Nigeria.

This reviewed literature indicates that VON's digital-era transformation involves redesigning of its operational and managerial structures, integrating digital technologies into content, navigating infrastructural challenges and adopting strategies to remain

competitive and relevant globally. While VON has made significant progress, especially in structural adaptation and digital integration, its effectiveness is still limited by funding constraints, infrastructural weaknesses and the need for deeper audience engagement. Addressing these challenges will be essential for sustaining its role as Nigeria's authoritative voice in the global media environment.

Methodology

A qualitative research design was adopted to examine VON's operational and managerial structures and their adaptation to the digital era (Campbell *et al* 2020). The study population comprised all VON management staff. From this, 20 serving and retired top management personnel were purposively selected across key departments, including News, Digital Media, Languages, Operations, Engineering, IT, HR, SPCD and Finance & Administration, to ensure diversity of perspectives and institutional memory.

Primary data were obtained through semi-structured interviews, while secondary data were drawn from VON's official documents, policy reports, and relevant literature (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Interviews, averaging 20-30 minutes, were conducted in Abuja and Lagos, with retired staff engaged virtually where necessary. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality was assured. Data were analysed using thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2019) framework, with an inductive approach applied to identify patterns of convergence and divergence in respondents' views. These insights were compared with the literature review to inform the findings and discussion.

Findings

RQ1: What are the operational and managerial structures of VON and do they support digital broadcasting?

Sixteen respondents (Respondents 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 18, 19 and 20) affirmed that VON's structure supports both analogue and digital workflows. For example, Respondent 1 noted, "The existing departmental arrangement enables smooth coordination between analogue and digital operations." Respondent 2 explained, "VON operates under hierarchical structure and uses unguided copy that matches the McKinsey model where performance relies mainly on the leadership of corporation, departments and units."

Similarly, Respondent 13 stated, "The Digital Media Department works closely with News and Operations, which makes digital broadcasting feasible." Eleven respondents (Respondents 3, 7, 8, 9, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, and 20) acknowledged that despite VON's operational alignment with digital broadcasting, misalignment in the top executive leadership of the Corporation (appointment of CEO with no sufficient broadcast knowledge or experience) since 2015 to date has not only weakened VON, but silenced it in the global broadcast media landscape. Respondent 14 stated, "We are no longer broadcasting in VON, we are rather 'broadcrashing.'" (a word Respondent 14 coined to describe the mass operational failure in VON due to top executive leadership misalignment.

Five respondents (Respondents 2, 6, 9, 12 and 15) cautioned that departmental silos sometimes hinder integration. As Respondent 6 explained, "Some units still operate in isolation, slowing down the full shift to digital." Three respondents (Respondents 14,

17, and 19) believed the structure remains analogue-oriented. Respondent 17 observed, “Our structure is still largely traditional and needs reorganisation to fully embrace digital workflows.”

RQ2: To what extent has VON integrated digital technologies into its content production and distribution processes?

Fourteen respondents (Respondents 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 12, 13, 15, 16, 18, and 20) reported substantial integration. Respondent 5 remarked, “We now use digital audio workstations and stream most programmes online.” Respondent 10 added, “Social media platforms have become central to distributing our content globally.”

Four respondents (Respondents 4, 8, 11 and 19) described partial integration, with gaps in training or equipment. Respondent 4 commented, “We are moving digital, but many staff still lack proper training.” Two respondents (Respondents 14 and 17) viewed adoption as minimal. Respondent 14 stressed, “Digital tools are unevenly used across departments, which creates inconsistency.”

RQ3: What challenges does VON encounter in restructuring its operations for digital age?

Nineteen respondents (Respondents 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20) cited inadequate funding. Respondent 8 stated, “Budget constraints slow our transition to advanced digital platforms.” Seventeen respondents (Respondents 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19, and 20) pointed to limited staff training and resistance to change. Respondent 3 observed, “Older staff members find it difficult to adapt to new technologies.” Fourteen respondents (Respondents 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, and 18) mentioned outdated infrastructure and bureaucracy. As Respondent 9 put it, “The approval process for new equipment is too slow, leaving us behind competitors.”

RQ4: What strategies has VON adopted to remain relevant and competitive globally?

Eleven respondents (Respondents 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 12, 15, and 20) cited increased digital content production and online presence. Respondent 2 stated, “VON has diversified its means of disseminating broadcast content to its audiences globally. We are on various social media platforms like YouTube, Facebook, X (formerly Twitter) and TikTok. Through our app, listeners can listen to us on Simple Radio, Radio Garden and TuneIn.” Six respondents (Respondents 4, 8, 11, 13, 16 and 18) highlighted strategic partnerships. Respondent 13 remarked, “Collaborations with international broadcasters have enhanced our expertise and visibility.”

Five respondents (Respondents 7, 9, 14, 15, and 18) said VON’s top executive management no longer follows up the Corporation’s partnerships and agreements with international organisations. Respondent 15 emphasised, “As an international radio station, our past CEOs from inception to 2015, signed a number of MoUs with some international bodies. Through that, VON staff got several opportunities abroad.” Respondent 18 affirmed, “Since 2015 to date, VON pays no or less attention to these

MoUs; and the result is that staff have been deprived of many opportunities abroad.” Three respondents (Respondents 14, 17, and 19) pointed to staff training. Respondent 19 commented, “Regular workshops are building our team’s digital competencies.” Although, respondent 1 made an exemption: “There is disparity in training opportunities. For example, VON staff in Abuja are favoured more in training opportunities than their counterparts in VON Lagos and zonal offices.”

Theme	Frequency of Mentions (out of 20 respondents)	Respondents	Illustrative Quotes
Digital Integration Efforts	12	Respondents 8, 10, others	“The IT and Digital Media departments have helped integrate digital processes into VON’s workflow, but the overall structure remains largely traditional” (Respondent 8). “The station has embraced some digital initiatives, especially in news production and online content dissemination, but it is yet to fully transition to a digital-first model” (Respondent 10).
Funding Constraints	15	Respondents 14, 12, others	“Inadequate funding limits the station’s ability to upgrade equipment, train staff and sustain digital transmission projects” (Respondent 14) “VON has the human resources and expertise, but the absence of consistent government support makes progress uneven.” (Respondent 12)
Managerial Rigidity	10	Respondents 2, 6, others	“The system is too rigid and bureaucratic, slowing down innovation and preventing quick adaptation to digital technologies.” (Respondent 2) “Decision-making is overly centralised, making it difficult for technical departments to implement changes promptly.” (Respondent 6)
Hybrid Operational Structure	General consensus	All respondents in varying degrees	“Digital elements have been introduced, but legacy bureaucratic practices and resource limitations continue to dominate operations.”

Discussion

The findings revealed that VON operates a hierarchical structure, supervised at the top by the Minister of Information and National Orientation and a Board of Directors whose members are appointed by the President, while the Director-General oversees day-to-day operations. This structure aligns with the media ecology theory, which suggests that the organisational environment influences operational efficiency and audience engagement. Although, it justifies the McKinsey model, which is the structure used in VON, as stated by Respondent 2, it however, creates unnecessary barriers for rapid organisational progress.

The operational expansion of VON, including offices in six geopolitical zones and bureaus abroad, reflects a response to environmental pressures, consistent with the Media Ecology assertion that media houses must adapt structurally to ecosystem-level changes (Madouh & Kwon, 2023). Respondent 14 confirmed, “VON bureau offices were established in South Africa...” While geographical structural expansions are good for the growth of an organisation, there are also financial implications, except if they are asset-driven. This informs why VON office in South Africa was closed, and why VON could not set up offices in the United States of America and United Kingdom due to funding challenges, as confirmed by nineteen respondents.

Arguably, in addition to the underfunding state of VON, there are also concerns about how the international radio station manages the monthly and annual allocations it receives from the Federal Government of Nigeria. Therefore, misappropriation of these funds may account for the digital and technological infrastructural deficits as well as the upskilling gaps in VON.

In line with these financial and managerial challenges, the findings also converge with empirical studies on the restructuring of broadcast media. For instance, Rostamian and Moradi Kamreh (2024) found that aligning organisational structures with digital technologies enhances content production and operational efficiency. VON’s creation of the Digital Media Department and IT unit reflects such global practices, suggesting attempts at structural adaptation to digital broadcasting demands.

However, divergence remains in the pace and effectiveness of implementation. While international studies emphasise smooth structural integration, some VON respondents (e.g., Respondent 17) pointed to persistent operational misalignment: *“The once authoritative choice has lost its relevance due to misalignment in leadership.”*

The study found that all 20 respondents confirmed substantial integration of digital technologies into VON’s content operations. Digital platforms include the VON website, mobile app, YouTube, Facebook, TikTok, and X (formerly Twitter). Respondent 1 emphasised, “VON has incorporated web publishing, social media engagement, live streaming, and a mobile application into its structure.” Respondent 16 affirmed that: “VON’s structures align with digital broadcasting on almost all fronts.” This finding is also in consonance with the Media Convergence Theory, which posits that integrating channels and redesigning content enhances audience reach and interactivity (Hase, Boczek & Scharrow, 2023; Nielsen & Fletcher, 2023). It also converges with Zondi (2024), who found that digital technologies extend reach and facilitate audience interaction. Similarly, Egbuna & Iyamu (2020) highlighted VON’s hybrid operations, combining online platforms and shortwave frequencies.

Divergence, however, is observed in the quality and extent of integration. Respondent 8 noted, “VON website is not up to standard...sometimes crashes...no audios or videos on the website to compete favourably.” Similar to VON’s inability to maintain its bureau office in South Africa and establish new ones in America and United Kingdom, it could be that underfunding or mismanagement of funds was responsible for lack of a standard website for VON as an international radio station. While international cases demonstrate smoother digital transitions (Rostamian & Moradi Kamreh, 2024), VON’s digital workflow is constrained by infrastructural limitations and training gaps.

Respondents identified multiple barriers to digital transformation, notably funding constraints, outdated infrastructure, inadequate training, and regulatory restrictions. Respondent 1 highlighted, *“Budget constraints and delayed funding cycles...Skills and workflow gaps...staff require retraining and new tools to adapt to multiplatform content delivery under NBC compliance requirements.”* Respondent 16 further emphasised staffing and compensation issues: “The pay package itself is not attractive enough to retain those who have acquired the skills and knowledge...VON itself as an international broadcaster should also be on a separate unique salary structure.” These findings converge with Nigerian studies (Sanusi, Oyegoke & Ojewumi, 2025; Hassan & Sam, 2024), which report funding, digital literacy, and infrastructural deficits as persistent challenges in broadcast media. Globally, Dragomir & Túñez López (2024) note that even well-funded PSMs struggle with balancing technological innovation and institutional mandates; for VON, this challenge is exacerbated by legal limitations on commercial advertising under the VON Decree 15 of 1991 (Egbuna & Iyamu, 2020).

A divergence is evident in audience engagement practices. While Harliantara et al. (2025) reported proactive use of online platforms to satisfy audience preferences, VON’s engagement, though growing, remains limited due to network instability and low digital literacy among some staff, as Respondent 12 observed: “Poor listener engagement...production team must come up with content that will stimulate listeners to engage our platforms.” VON has adopted multiple strategies to maintain relevance, including multiplatform distribution, mobile engagement, DRM shortwave reactivation,

and strategic partnerships. Respondent 1 summarised, “Website, live streaming, YouTube presence...collaboration with institutions and foreign missions strengthens content exchange and soft-power positioning.” Respondent 11 confirmed prominence of online broadcasts: “Online broadcasts are now given prominence via the VON app and live streaming...broadcasts on Facebook, X, Tik Tok, YouTube, and Spotify.”

These strategies are in accordance with Media Convergence Theory’s emphasis on redesigning content and integrating channels for compatibility and interactivity. They also resonate with global trends observed in Rostamian & Moradi Kamreh (2024) and Harliantara *et al* (2025), showing that structural adaptation and technology adoption are key to sustaining competitiveness. Divergence arises in bureaucratic and funding challenges; Respondent 8 noted, “Bureaucratic bottleneck in government institutions slows down the prompt implementation of policies that could be beneficial to the Digital transformation of VON.” This reflects a local constraint not emphasised in many international cases.

VON’s structural adaptation, creation of digital departments, and digital platform integration align with global evidence that organisational restructuring and convergence technologies enhance operational efficiency and audience engagement (Rostamian & Moradi Kamreh, 2024; Zondi, 2024; Harliantara *et al* 2025). Thus, unlike some international broadcasters, VON faces persistent challenges from funding limitations, bureaucratic bottlenecks, legal restrictions on commercial operations and inconsistent staff training, which affect full digital integration and audience engagement.

Conclusion

This study examined the organisational and managerial structures of VON, its integration of digital technologies, challenges in restructuring and strategies for global competitiveness. Findings revealed that VON operates a hierarchical, state-supervised structure with expansion across Nigeria’s geopolitical zones and select international bureaus. The creation of Digital Media and IT Departments reflects an organisational redesign aimed at adapting to the digital era, consistent with Media Ecology and Media Convergence theories. Most respondents confirmed substantial digital integration, including online platforms, live streaming, mobile applications, and social media engagement. However, challenges such as funding deficits, outdated infrastructure, inadequate staff training, bureaucratic bottlenecks and legal restrictions continue to limit the full potential of digital transformation at VON. VON’s strategies for remaining relevant and competitive globally, including multiplatform distribution, DRM reactivation, audience engagement and strategic partnerships, demonstrate a clear commitment to sustaining its authority as Nigeria’s international broadcaster. Nonetheless, structural and operational bottlenecks underscore the need for focused reforms to strengthen both digital and managerial capacities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance VON’s operations and global competitiveness:

1. The Federal Government should provide consistent and adequate funding to support digital infrastructure, staff training, and technological upgrades.
2. The Nigerian Presidency should be appointing one of the directors in VON's key departments as the CEOs of the Corporation. However, if the government wants to appoint someone outside VON, then such an individual must, as a matter of necessity and obligation, meet the NBC criteria for appointment, which is fifteen years of broadcast experience.
3. Continuous professional development programmes, both locally and internationally, should be instituted to improve staff skills in digital content production, platform management and audience engagement.
4. Investment in reliable servers, high-speed broadband, multimedia production equipment and mobile platforms will ensure seamless content production and distribution.
5. Amendments to the VON Decree and related regulations should be considered to allow limited commercial activities, which can generate additional revenue for sustainable operations.
6. Develop targeted strategies for interactive audience participation across social media and digital platforms to enhance relevance, reach and feedback-driven content improvements.
7. VON should restore its partnerships with relevant international agencies and collaborate with global media organisations, tech firms and educational institutions to exchange programmes and manpower experiences and adopt best practices.
8. Establish internal monitoring and evaluation systems to assess digital transformation progress, identify bottlenecks, and align organisational goals with emerging technological trends.

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